

INTERLANGUAGE CODE

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Annotatsiya

Bu maqolamizda tillararo kod, ularning almashinuvi va kelib chiqish sabablari, tillararo almashinuv sirtining paydo bo'ladigan talablari, so'zning qiyinligini tahlil qilish. O'sha davr olimlari va ularning hozirgi qarashlari haqida intervensiya.

Kalit so'zlar: tillararo kod, interferensiya sinxronligi va dinamikasi, tinish belgilari, leksik, morfologik, sintaktik, semantik (reallik, noaniqlik, sinonimiya) nutq,

Аннотация

Это в нашей статье межъязыковой код, причины их обмена и происхождения, возникающие требования к поверхности межъязыкового обмена, способы анализа сложности слова. Выступление об ученых того времени и их нынешних взглядах.

Ключевые слова: межъязыковой код, интерференционная синхронность и динамика, пунктуация, лексическая, морфологическая, синтаксическая, семантическая (действительность, многозначность, синонимия) речь,

Abstract

This is it in our article interlanguage code , their exchange and their come exit reasons , interlanguage of exchange surface came requirements difficulties how analysis to do about soz held . Interference about and their present of the day scientists views .

Key words : interlinguistic code, interference synchrony and dynamics, punctuation, lexical, morphological, syntactic, semantic (realities, ambiguity, synonymy) speech,

How to analyze student difficulties caused by interference ? Interference , as well as positive transfer, can cover all levels of language: phonetic, grammatical, lexical, orthographic, and has a significant impact on the development of speech activity in a new language. Types of interference differ according to several criteria (Kovylina LN, Selinker L., Makei VF, Kitrosskaya II and others). Interference can be communicatively important, that is, breaking the mutual understanding of interlocutors, and communicatively insignificant, not interfering with mutual understanding. Interference can be synchronous or

dynamic. Synchronous noise is constant. He always stays with the student, for example, his accent. Dynamic interference chronologically precedes the first type, it reflects the process of the student's progressive movement in language acquisition and can be overcome. According to the types associated with the specific characteristics of speech activity, they distinguish productive (in speech production) and receptive interference (in comprehension). Interference with productive types of speech activity helps direct observation and is more evident than with receptive types of speech. Combinatorial and modifier interference are distinguished according to the nature of speech deviation. Combinatorial interference is the presence of other language system elements in speech or the organization of language elements according to the laws of other systems. Modifier interference leads to the appearance in the linguistic element of the features or properties of the correlating element of another system, for example, phonemic features or features of a grammatical class: the pronunciation of French [t] with an aspiration to English, or the pronunciation of a French noun common to its Russian counterpart.

Finally, the types of interference differ according to language subsystems: according to the language and speech levels where it occurs. This interference is sound (phonetic or phonological), spelling, punctuation, lexical, morphological, syntactic, semantic (realities, ambiguity, synonymy, homonymy), stylistic (functional styles), cultural or socio-cultural. Helping the student to overcome the interference for, the teacher must imagine what, from which language it is taken, to which level the imported element belongs, and what the speaker does with it: simple replacement or modification. The results of the analysis of the influence of the mother and first foreign languages on the second foreign language are included in a table similar to the table. Change the unit of the second foreign language by local or first foreign modification. Interference replacement is possible in two forms: unit replacement and structural replacement. Unit replacement - this is the transfer of the donor language unit to the recipient language, sometimes with the change of the received word according to the phonological or grammatical laws of the recipient language. Structural replacement is to transfer the syntactic structure of the donor language to the recipient language. Let's give some examples.

Cultural interference is caused not by the language system itself, but by the culture that the language reflects. In different cultures, similar realities, events, norms of behavior, for example, unequal forms of speech etiquette can lead to interference. Thus, in Russian, "please" is used as a polite formula, which has the

nuance of meaning "for nothing", used as a response to "thank you". In English and French, "please" and "s" il vous plait "do not have these meanings. Depending on the order of language learning, the confusion caused by this inconsistency in speech practice is more or less. In this case, from English then learning French, cultural transfer is more likely from FL1, because European communities are similar in many ways in the level of everyday culture. Of great importance is the level of socio-cultural skills of the first foreign language. The higher it is, the higher the probability of positive transfer.

Semantic interference occurs due to the fact that events known to the speaker are reflected differently in the new language than in the known languages. For example, Russian students call brown bread instead of pain bis in French noir. English as a first foreign language increases the likelihood of mixing (brown bread). By nature, semantic interference is often substituted. This can be expressed in the introduction of not only foreign language units, but also structures. A common type of such interference is when students try to translate Russian or English proverbs, sayings and phrases into French word for word. Lexical interference is the introduction of foreign vocabulary into speech in a new language. The source of noise in learning French on the basis of Russian and English is, as a rule, the first foreign language. Some lexical units of foreign languages are very similar, therefore, in similar conditions for the development of lexemes (school education in both cases), the probability of such interference is high. Lexical interference can be both modifying and substituting. Modification interference is, for example, the expansion or narrowing of the meaning of a lexical unit of the new language by analogy with a similar unit in the donor language. Frequency switching interference is the transfer of similar lexical units into a new language with processing according to the phonetic model of the receiving language, for example, the "ix tiro" of the verb "rester" in the sense of "rest". English "to rest" Grammatical interference is as common as lexical interference in second foreign language acquisition. The nature of grammatical interference differs in morphology and syntax.

Morphological interference is a deviation from the norm observed in speech, associated with the violation of the categorical signs of speech fragments, which occurs under the influence of the relevant categories of the interfering language. Deviation from the norm can be both formal (for example, mistakes in conjugation) and functional (incorrect use of grammatical forms). Modification interference is a change in the form or function of a recipient language morpheme according to the grammatical model of the donor language.

An example. Giving the common features of the Russian word to the French noun. Substitutional interference is the use of donor language morphemes in the recipient language, as well as the use of donor language grammatical relations for recipient language morphemes, or ignoring the new language's grammatical relations. prototype in already known languages. For example, in the area of French verb conjugation, students show a strong tendency to forget the ending of the second person present tense -s. This shows the influence of English, where the second person of the verb does not have a specific ending, unlike the third person. A typical error attributed to morphological interference is the incorrect control of the verb, that is, the use of inappropriate prefixes between the verb and its object, for example, the French auxiliary verb *a* with the preposition *o* is used with analogy. Russian "to help someone". Many misuses of prepositions and articles are caused by this type of interference. Thus, at the beginning of learning, the French expression "dans la rue" always becomes the object of interference with Russian and English "on the street", "on the street". For students who know French, a similar interference is observed in English as a second foreign language: on page five (instead of page five) by analogy with French *a la page cinq* and Russian. on page five. Grammatical syntactic intervention is associated with a violation of the compatibility of the recipient language elements in the speech chain under the influence of the compatibility models of the donor language. It manifests itself in unconscious imitation of the syntactic structures of PR or FL1. For example, the use of grammatical structures such as "une des plus grandes jamais vues dans la region" is derived from the English "one of the largest ever seen in this region" trail paper. Imitation of syntactic structures is expressed in the three most common types of syntactic constructions. First, it is plus-segmentation, that is, the increase of elements in the receiving language under the influence of the distributional rules of the donor language (rules of compatibility of language units). For example, the use of additional negative: "Je ne vois pas aucune difference". Secondly, this is minus segmentation, that is, a reduction in the number of elements in the receiving language under the influence of relevant models of the donor language. For example, the exclusion of the linking verb *etre* in a compound nominal predicate. Finally, substitution is possible, that is, rearrangement of the elements of the model of the receiving language under the influence of the rules of the donor language. A common case of this intervention is to place any French adjective before the noun in the English and Russian case 1.

is manifested in the intonation pattern of speech, its rhythm and articulation of phonemes. This is also noticeable in the accentuation of speech (deve "deve "deve "placement place of dev-elope" ment), change of the type of assimilation (progressive in English, regressive in French) and others. Incorrect articulation together with intonation creates a foreign accent. difficult to overcome . Articulation of native or first foreign phonemes instead of FL2 phonemes is a common phonetic interference of substitution type. For example, the pronunciation of the palatalized Russian phoneme [l "] instead of the associated French sound. The change in phonetic interference occurs through a mixture of phonemic features and leads to the formation of specific allophones that can be used with high precision. to say in what sequence a certain person learned foreign languages. Such an allophone, for example, the pronunciation of French [t] with English aspiration .

is the perception of phonemic features of a foreign language as unique and redundant. A distinctive feature distinguishes (distinguishes) two phonemes of the same language. For example, it differs in terms of nasality. The lack of differentiation of such a sign, taking it as unimportant (excessive) leads to incorrect articulation of the sound. Graphical and orthographic interference manifests itself in writing: the rules of writing words of another language are transferred to the target language. This results in spelling errors and graphic inconsistencies. This noise is very common because a large part of the common and related vocabulary in English and French encourages the student to make mistakes:

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